

Multiple Perspectives on Barriers to Care of People Living with Haemophilia in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Evidence shows that most people living with haemophilia (PLwH) in Nigeria do not know enough about the condition and face some barriers. **Objectives:** This study explored the barriers related to the care of PLwH, as a part of a needs assessment study. **Methodology:** This exploratory mixed methods study used surveys and focus group discussions (FGD) to evaluate the perceptions of educational, technical, financial and psychosocial barriers facing PLwH. Participants included haemophilia patients (i.e. PLwH) and healthcare providers (HCP) in southern Nigeria. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential, while thematic analysis was used for qualitative data. **Results:** A total of 219 individuals participated in the study (PLwH – 130; HCP – 89). There were divergent views between the two groups of participants (i.e. PLwH and HCPs) regarding the educational barriers. About 51% (66/130) of PLwH agreed that the HCPs did not provide them with adequate education about haemophilia while only 33% (30/89) of HCPs shared that view; $Z = 2.5619$ with p -value of 0.01. Many participants in both groups agree that HCPs generally lacked adequate training to manage haemophilia (PLwH-46%, 60/130; HCP – 46%, 41/89). Significantly more HCPs (76% of 89) agreed that PLwH had challenges related to access of basic treatment (i.e. clotting factors) compared to the perception of PLwH (60% of 130), $Z = 2.42$ and $p=0.007$. Some common themes from the data included public awareness, access to medications, challenges with lifestyle and anxiety/depression.

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Conclusion: Although hemophilia is a rare disease it affects a significant number of people in Nigeria to warrant increasing attention. This mixed methods study sought to explore the barriers related to haemophilia in southern Nigeria. One approach to address the educational barriers is to invest in the continuing education of HCPs. Expanding the number of haemophilia treatment centers in Nigeria would help address many technical barriers.

Keywords: Haemophilia, Self care, Needs assessment, Focus groups, Continuing education, Perception, Health services accessibility

INTRODUCTION

Haemophilia is a relatively rare, X-linked inherited bleeding disorder caused by a deficiency of functional coagulation factor VIII (haemophilia A) or factor IX (haemophilia B). Clinically, haemophilia can be classified as severe haemophilia (defined as a residual clotting factor activity of less than 1%), moderate-severe haemophilia (between 1% and 5%), and mild haemophilia (between 6% and 40%).¹ A 2021 survey identified 630 people living with haemophilia (PLwH) in Nigeria, with a national population of 206,000,000, giving a prevalence of 3 cases per 1 million.² People living with severe haemophilia present with spontaneous joint and muscle bleeding leading to joint damage, resulting in higher emergency room visits and hospitalization compared to the rest of the population.³ The treatment for haemophilia includes regular infusion with coagulation factor concentrates or or newer nonfactor blood products, such as emicizumab, fitusiran and concizumab.⁴

Almost 40% of PLwH in Nigeria were rated to have poor health status and research shows that almost 50% of this population in Nigeria were hospitalized within 12 months.^{5,6} Despite this trend, evidence shows that most people living

with haemophilia in Nigeria as well as many healthcare providers do not know enough about the condition.³ Previous research identified barriers that are faced by haemophilia patients globally. They include educational barriers, such as lack of awareness among patients regarding the disease symptoms and course as well as inconvenience and scheduling barriers, where caregiver may not be available as needed. Financial barrier often exists, where patients can neither pay for the clotting factors nor the logistics needed to receive donated clotting factor products as well as psychosocial barriers.⁷ However, there is no Nigerian research to show the extent of barriers faced by patients and their families related to haemophilia.

This article sought to describe the pattern of barriers faced by PLwH in Nigeria, from the perspectives of patients/caregivers (i.e. PLwH) and healthcare providers (HCP). It was a part of a larger needs assessment study. The research objectives were to: Ascertain attitudes toward, and behaviours associated with key prevention activities, as well as barriers to accessing novel treatments among PLwH and caregivers; Understand the self-reported health status of PLwH in Nigeria; Evaluate the barriers experienced by HCP regarding the management of hemophilia; and proffer solutions to the barriers to learning about the clinical needs for PLwH in Nigeria.

To the best of authors' knowledge, there are no previous studies that evaluated the perceptions of barrier among PLwH and caregivers in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This was an exploratory mixed methods study, involving surveys and focus group discussions (FGD),⁸ to evaluate the perspectives of PLwH and HCPs on haemophilia-related barriers that PLwH encounter (Objective #1). The mixed methods

design has been used in the past to explore multiple perspectives related to a health outcome in Nigeria.⁹ The surveys had a mix of structured and open-ended questions which assessed (a) compliance with recommended prevention behaviours; (b) self-management of haemophilia; (c) beliefs and practices related to dealing with joint disease and infections; and (d) self-reported evaluation of health status (Objective #2). The surveys were deployed online, through telephone, and on paper at hospitals that manage haemophilia. A section of the survey evaluated the providers' practice patterns, self-reported learning needs, and perceived barriers to providing care to PLwH.

After completing the survey, interested participants were requested to join the FGD to further explore the depth of their understanding of the questions, the barriers they faced and how they might be overcome. The FGD were recorded and transcribed to further analyze the data. Focus group discussions with HCPs and PLwH were used to explore the usefulness of some evidence-based approaches to improving provider competence and self-management procedure for the PLwH.

Study Setting and Participants

This study was focused on southern Nigeria, with emphasis on the southeast and south-south regions although people participated from other parts of the country due to the online nature of the survey. The target participants in this project include the following groups:

People living with hemophilia and their caregivers- These include family members of the PLwH, with age ranging between 18 and 60 years.

Healthcare providers (HCP) involved in managing haemophilia- These include physicians, nurses, pharmacists, community health workers and laboratory scientists.

A minimum sample size of 139 participants is required to determine the mean haemophilia-related knowledge score with 0.5 precision and 95% confidence interval.¹⁰ Participants were recruited through patient associations (including the Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria) and hospitals that manage haemophilia in the study setting. Targeted social media adverts and posts in relevant WhatsApp groups were also used to recruit participants within the region. Consenting participants were required to complete the online survey.

Study Instruments Development and Testing

The instruments used in this mixed methods study were developed through a review of relevant literature. Different instruments were developed for each group of participants, i.e. PLwH and HCP. The PLwH survey had 25 items that were grouped into demographics, educational barriers, technical barriers, financial barriers, perception of stigma and knowledge quiz. Similarly, the HCP survey had 25 items that were grouped into demographics, educational barriers, technical barriers, financial barriers, psychosocial barriers and knowledge quiz.⁷ The educational barriers considered awareness about haemophilia, knowledge of symptoms and access to information about the disease. Technical barriers studied included adequacy of number of clinicians, challenges with laboratory diagnosis and challenges with storage of treatment products.

Regarding the financial barriers, the study acknowledged that haemophilia patients in Nigeria are unable to afford clotting factors and thus receive them as donations through the Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria.³ However, they are required to pay for logistics (e.g. transportation of the Clotting factors to their nearest treatment centres) to access the treatment. The financial barriers considered were access to basic treatment (e.g. logistics to obtain donated clotting factors), access to newer agents (e.g.

emicizumab)⁴ as well as the general cost of living as they relate to prioritizing haemophilia treatment over other healthcare needs. The psychosocial barriers included perceptions of stigma, mental health challenges (e.g. anxiety and depression) as well as access to counselling services.

After the instruments were developed, they were circulated among a panel of eight experts (including PLwH) to evaluate their face validity. Face validity is the subjective estimation regarding the clarity of an instrument. The instrument development protocol and testing have been reported in the literature.¹¹

Ethical Consideration

Ethics approval for this project was obtained from the Human Research Ethics Committee at the Abia State Ministry of Health (May 31, 2023) as well as the Ethics Committee at Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria (February 19, 2024). This research did not collect personal health information, outside of the study instrument. All potential participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study before joining the

course. Research data was managed according to international standards. Although individuals who participated in the focus group discussion did not remain anonymous, pseudonyms were assigned to protect their identity. The project team ensured high ethical standards, including respect for human dignity; respect for free and informed consent; respect for vulnerable persons; respect for privacy and confidentiality; respect for justice and inclusiveness; and, balancing harms and benefits by minimizing harm and maximizing benefits.

RESULTS

Demographics

A total of 219 individuals participated in the survey (PLwH - 130; HCP - 89). For the PLwH/caregivers, their average age was 28±11 years and had been associated with haemophilia for about 6 years (IQR: 2,12). Whereas the average years in practice for the HCPs was 10±8 years and had encountered about 20 patients (IQR: 6, 32) with haematologic disorders in the previous month. Table 1 shows the demographics of the PLwH while Table 2 shows the demographics of the HCP who participated in the project.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of participants in PLwH survey

Attributes for PLwH survey (n=130)	Number (%)
Description	
Patients	25 (19.23)
Family member	99 (76.15)
Friends	6 (4.62)
Age distribution (±standard deviation)	
Patients	20.40 (±8.02)
Family member	30.27 (±11.76)
Friends	27.50 (±5.39)
Years involved with haemophilia	
Patients	11.84 (±7.80)
Family member	4.70 (±6.11)
Friends	4.17 (±2.04)
Geopolitical zone of residence	
North-Central	12 (9.23%)
North-East	12 (9.23%)
North-West	10 (7.69%)
South-East	34 (26.15%)
South-South	33 (25.38%)
South-West	29 (22.31%)

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of participants in HCP Survey

Attribute for HCP Survey (n=89)	Number (%)
Profession	
Doctors	46 (51.69%)
Laboratory staff	5 (5.62%)
Nurses	17 (19.10%)
Pharmacists	4 (4.49%)
Other healthcare professionals	11 (12.36%)
Students	6 (6.74%)
Location of practice	
Teaching hospital	62 (69.66%)
Other public health institutions	10 (11.24%)
Private /Missionary institution	9 (10.11%)
Student	8 (8.99%)
Geopolitical zone of practice	
South-East	48 (53.93%)
South-South	31 (34.83%)
Others	10 (11.24%)
Years in practice (±standard deviation)	
Doctors	12.91 (±6.01)
Laboratory staff	13.40 (±6.73)
Nurses	9.00 (±11.20)
Pharmacists	3.50 (±6.35)
Other healthcare professionals	7.18 (±4.62)
Students	0.00 0.00

Multiple Perspectives on Barriers Facing People Living with Hemophilia (Quantitative Findings)

The following results describe the perceptions of barriers in the educational, technical, psychological and financial domains from the viewpoints of PLwH and HCPs.

Perceptions about educational barriers

There were divergent views between the two groups of participants (i.e. PLwH and HCPs) regarding the educational barriers. Almost 55% (71/130) of all PLwH thought they had a poor understanding of the cause of the disease whereas most HCPs (52%, 45/89) thought the patients had a good understanding. Also, 51% (66/130) of PLwH agreed that the HCPs did not provide them with adequate education about haemophilia while only 33% (30/89) of HCPs shared that view;

$Z = 2.5619$ with p -value of 0.01. Figure 1 shows the perceptions about educational barriers.

Figure 1. Comparison of perception of psychosocial barriers between PLwH and HCPs in Nigeria

Perceptions about technical barriers

The views of PLwH and HCPs were largely aligned regarding the technical barriers. Many participants in both groups agree that HCPs generally lacked adequate training to manage haemophilia (PLwH-46%, 60/130; HCP - 46%, 41/89) and that the storage of treatment products was a challenge (PLwH-50%, 64/130; HCP - 57%, 51/89). There was no significant difference in the perception of laboratory challenges ($Z = 1.76$ with p -value of 0.07). Figure 2 shows the perceptions on technical barriers.

Fig 2

Perceptions about financial barriers

Both groups of participants had similar views regarding the financial barriers. Significantly more HCPs (76% of 89) agreed that PLwH had

challenges related to access of basic treatment (i.e. clotting factors) compared to the perception of PLwH (60% of 130), $Z = 2.42$ and $p=0.007$. More PLwH (69/6% of 130) than HCPs (54.5% of 89) thought that the high cost of living in Nigeria was a barrier, $Z = 2.28$ and $p=0.02$. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the perceptions on financial barriers.

Fig 3

Perceptions about psychosocial barriers

There were divergent views between the two groups of participants (i.e. PLwH and HCPs) regarding the psychosocial barriers. Significantly more HCPs (71.3% of 89) agreed that PLwH had challenges related to mental health compared to the perception of PLwH (38.4% of 130), $Z = -4.79$ and $p<0.001$. Although fewer PLwH (31.2%, 71/130) perceived stigma to be a barrier compared to almost 43% of all HCPs, this difference was not statistically significant; $Z = -1.9043$ with p -value of 0.06. Figure 4 shows the perceptions about psychosocial barriers.

Multiple perspectives: Qualitative Findings

A purposive sample of 15 individuals (PLwH=20, HCP=15) participated in three separate focus group discussions. Other survey participants (PLwH=80, HCP=50) provided comments regarding their experiences on each of the four domains of the questionnaire, i.e. educational, technical, financial and psychosocial barriers. This section provides the findings from deductive thematic analysis of the qualitative data. The main themes were educational, technical, financial and psychosocial barriers and recommendations.

Theme: educational barriers

Educational barriers included sub-themes of public awareness, patient education about disease, experiences with symptoms, and perceptions of self-care.

There were 30 references to educational barriers. Many patients described the lack of or limited education that they have received regarding the condition. Some HCPs also remarked on the 'denial' they observed among patients.

Sub-theme: public awareness

This sub-theme focused on issues of public awareness about haemophilia. Some comments included:

"Awareness is not being made to the public for a better understanding of the condition" (patient).

"There is a lack of awareness of the sickness by the general public" (patient).

"Apart from healthcare providers giving information in the hospital, there's little awareness about haemophilia in the community" (HCP).

Sub-theme: patient awareness

There were many references to poor awareness about the disease among PLwH. Some of the comments were:

"I've rarely been told anything about hemophilia" (patient).

"I did not know about this disease until later when I lost two of my children" (caregiver).

"Some socio-cultural beliefs and customs act as barriers" (HCP).

Theme: technical barriers

Within the theme of technical barriers, there were sub-themes regarding access to medication, challenges regarding travel to treatment centres, issues about laboratories, storage of drugs, and perceptions about the competence of healthcare providers.

Sub-theme: access to medications

There were 26 references regarding access to medications, especially factor concentrates. Most (88%, 23/26) of the comments focused on the limited availability of drugs. Some of the comments were:

"In the course of treating my children, I find it difficult because of lack of drugs" (patient).

"Sometimes there is late attendance and administration of drugs by health workers" (patient).

"The high cost of accessing factors, lack of treatment centres in all the Teaching Hospital which would have made treatment easy and cheap" (patient).

Sub-theme: travel/distance

Many PLwH and HCPs referred to challenges with the distance to treatment centres and general difficulties with travel within Nigeria.

The following comments relate to this sub-theme:

"Considering the distance and road hazards, e.g. kidnapping on the road, COVID-19 lockdown, etc, it has become difficult for me to receive adequate care" (patient).

"Access to the treatment centre (hospital) is very far" (patient).

"Transportation problems (staying in public transport) because my knees can't bend" (patient).

Sub-theme: HCPs Competence

Among the 13 references to the education and skills of HCPs, 10 of the comments focused on their limited knowledge and competence, such as:

"There is a lack of trained personnel in general hospitals, primary health centres, comprehensive health centres and in the community" (HCP)

"[I have experienced] poor treatment and attention from health personnel" (patient).

Sub-theme: Storage of Drugs and Laboratory challenges

The challenges with power supply affecting the storage of samples were reported by PLwH and HCPs. Difficulties were also reported regarding laboratory diagnosis, as shown in the following comments:

"Lack of necessary technology in the lab" (Patient)

"High cost of reagents and fluctuating temperature for storage" (HCP)

"Poor storage of factors due to lack of electricity" (HCP)

Figure 5 is a Word Cloud showing the 100 most commonly used words relating to technical barriers.

Theme: financial barriers

Financial barriers included sub-themes about low income/poverty and the rising cost of services.

Some patients (n=8), reported difficulties with finding suitable employment due to the disease.

The issue of cost included patient-living costs (e.g. transportation) and health-facility costs (e.g. laboratory investigations).

Sub-theme: Low income

There appears to be a pattern where PLwH are unable to be gainfully employed due to disability from joint disease. The following comments speak to issues related to income and poverty:

"Not having a job is the only financial barrier that I have had" (patient).

"I don't have a job to earn so one can carry out needed tests" (patient).

"Most patients cannot pay their monthly dues [to Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria to offset the cost of logistics], the high cost of living, some don't even have transport fare" (patient).

Sub-theme: Cost of services

Many participants spoke to the cost of services associated with haemophilia care, especially the laboratory testing. The following comments are examples of found within this sub-theme:

"It is costly to treat" (Patient)

"High cost of [logistics to access] clotting factor products and the lack of insurance coverage" (HCP)

"High cost of laboratory reagent and fluctuating temperature for storage" (HCP)

Theme: psychosocial barriers

Psychosocial barriers focused on sub themes related to anxiety and depression, challenges related in lifestyle and family, perceptions of stigma as well as perceptions of support. The theme of recommendations focused on what needs to change in order to improve the care provided to PLwH.

Sub-theme: Challenges with lifestyle

PLwH expressed challenges in their lifestyle due to the disease. This ranged from limitations in recreation and school attendance to family difficulties with looking after sick children during periods of hospitalization.

“Sometimes when I have bleeds it prevents me from attending class activities” (patient)

“I am not attending school always and I also do not meet up in school activities [due to the disease]” (patient)

“I cannot engage in sports activities due to haemophilia” (patient)

Sub-theme: anxiety and depression

There were 13 (PLwH=10, HCP=3) references to fear, such as

“Fear of getting injured in social outings” (HCP),

“I have sleepless nights due to fear of bleeding”

(Patient), and ‘...The fear of bleeding as a result of being wounded” (patient)

Sub-theme: perception of stigma

PLwH made 10 references to stigma and isolation, with emphasis on the challenges with interpersonal relations due to the disease. Some of the references include:

“Stigmatization of children or family with haemophilia” (patient).

“Personally, as I patient there that there is social isolation that you feel because of your inability to do other things you were supposed to do as a normal person” (patient).

“There is frustration and isolation to avoid injuries and bleeding” (HCP)

Figure 6 shows the interconnection of the themes and sub-themes regarding barriers faced by people living with haemophilia in Nigeria.

Figure 6. Word tree showing interconnection of the themes and sub-themes related to hemophilia care in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The data showed that most of the people living with haemophilia (PLwH) were diagnosed later in life with an average duration of disease of 11.84 (± 7.80) years. The delay in diagnosing haemophilia in Nigeria has been previously reported^{3,12} and was attributed to the limited competence of healthcare providers regarding haemophilia diagnosis and treatment as well as low awareness by the public regarding the inheritance patterns and clinical features of the disease. The delayed diagnosis often causes patients to have poorer health outcomes. Research shows that almost 40% of PLwH in Nigeria were rated to have poor health status and that almost 50% of this population in Nigeria were hospitalized within 12 months.^{5,6}

Educational Barriers

PLwH face diverse educational barriers although HCPs and PLwH see these differently. The educational barriers considered awareness about haemophilia, knowledge of symptoms and access to information about the disease. The HCPs significantly overestimated the understanding of haemophilia by the patients, where most HCPs (52%, 45/89) thought the patients had a good understanding while only about 45% of the patients shared the same view. This mismatch could stem from the HCPs not providing adequate education to the patients about the disease. One patient said: “I've rarely been told anything about haemophilia”. Figure 1 further elaborates on this mismatch between HCPs' educational efforts and the patients' level of understanding. As previously reported, most

HCPs in Nigeria have poor understanding of hemophilia.³ Thus it is possible that this translates into poor patient education. Good patient education will translate to improved adherence to prophylactic treatment thus leading to improved patient outcomes.¹³ In order to improve patient education, it is important to invest in HCPs education.

Technical Barriers

Technical barriers studied included adequacy of the number of clinicians, challenges with laboratory diagnosis and storage of treatment products. Many participants in both groups agree that HCPs generally lacked adequate training to manage haemophilia (PLwH-46%, 60/130; HCP - 46%, 41/89). According to one participant, "There is a lack of trained personnel in general hospitals, primary health centres, comprehensive health centres and in the community". Although this is the first study to report on the lack of training on haemophilia management in Nigeria, the limited haemophilia awareness by HCPs has been previously reported.³ Participants also noted that storing treatment products was challenging (PLwH-50%, 64/130; HCP - 57%, 51/89). This is in line with the findings that were published by Tisher *et al.*¹⁴ who noted that ease of storage of haemophilia treatment products was a predictor of patient adherence and convenience of treatment. Some of the treatment factors require refrigeration but Nigeria is plagued by an unstable power supply.

Many patients often travel long distances to access treatment products and this can disrupt their adherence to care. According to one of the patients, "...I come from Imo State [to Enugu] and it has not been easy with me..." Meanwhile, patients face diverse barriers to accessing their care from distant treatment centers including the accessibility of public transportation. It is common practice in Nigeria for transporters to fit more passengers than recommended into small vehicles to increase their profits. This reduces legroom and poses safety challenges. Particularly,

this practice worsens joint pain for haemophilia patients. According to one of the participants, "...transportation problems (staying in public transport) because my knees can't bend..." It is therefore necessary to expand the number of haemophilia treatment centers in Nigeria. This will reduce the technical barriers facing patients and improve access to care.

Financial Barriers

In the past two years, the Nigerian economy has experienced its worst inflation on record. This causes prices to fluctuate, and unemployment and poverty to increase.¹⁵ The worsening economic outlook for Nigeria places significant financial barriers to PLwH. More PLwH (69.6% of 130) than HCPs (54.5% of 89) thought that the high cost of living in Nigeria was a barrier, $Z = 2.28$ and $p=0.02$. This scenario is further exemplified by the fact that some patients ($n=8$), reported difficulties with finding suitable employment due to the disease. In the words of one patient, "Not having a job is the only financial barrier that I have had" (patient). This means that to sustain the treatment of haemophilia in Nigeria, pharmaceutical companies need to extend their compassionate access programs to medicines, as the patient cannot afford treatment otherwise.

Furthermore, both groups of participants agreed that patients faced challenges with accessing basic treatment (i.e. clotting factors), however, significantly more HCPs (76% of 89) than PLwH (60% of 130) shared this perspective, $Z = 2.42$ and $p=0.007$. This difference might be due to the fact that the HCPs understand that the treatment products in Nigeria are donated and that the PLwH may never be able to afford their market value. The patients may not know about this reality as they do not see the complete picture. Presently, haemophilia treatment products in Nigeria are donated through the Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria and distributed through specific Haemophilia Treatment Centres.³ This

model needs to be sustained and possibly expanded to include new treatment centres, especially in southern Nigeria. According to one patient, “most patients cannot pay their monthly dues [to Haemophilia Foundation of Nigeria to offset the cost of logistics], the high cost of living, some don't even have transport fare” (patient). Feedback from HCPs showed that there is very limited access to novel therapies in Nigeria due to the lack of health insurance to pay for the treatments. Most of the patients are presently on the standard therapies although more could benefit from novel therapies if pharmaceutical companies would extend their compassionate access programs.

Psychosocial Barriers

The psychosocial barriers studied included perceptions of stigma, mental health challenges (e.g. anxiety and depression) as well as access to counselling services. This study found that there were divergent views between the two groups of participants (i.e. PLwH and HCPs) regarding the psychosocial barriers as significantly more HCPs (71.3% of 89) agreed that PLwH had challenges related to mental health compared to the perception of PLwH (38.4% of 130), $Z = -4.79$ and $p < 0.001$. Despite this, about 56% of HCPs and 33% of PLwH reported poor access to counselling services. This figure is lower than what was reported in the literature to show that up to 77% of haemophilia patients in Nigeria did not have access to a psychologist.^{3,12}

Anxiety and fears characterized the psychological concerns of patients, often due to changes in lifestyle. The lifestyle changes ranged from limitations in physical activities and school attendance to family difficulties with looking after sick children during periods of hospitalization. Although participation in physical activity among young PLwH is improving, research shows that physical activity levels in adults with haemophilia are lower compared to age-matched healthy

controls.(Zhou). This is similar to the findings in our study. According to some patients;

“Sometimes when I have bleed it prevents me from attending class activities” (patient)

“I am not attending school always and I also do not meet up in school activities [due to the disease]” (patient); “I cannot engage in sports activities due to haemophilia”. (patient) The limitations in physical activity might be a reflection of historical trends in living with haemophilia where patients were discouraged from participating in sports because of the high risk of bleeding when prophylactic treatment was not yet available. It also reflects the difficulty with care in Nigeria where access to treatment products is limited.^{3,12,16}

Given the chronic nature of haemophilia, many patients report higher psychological concerns. This is why effective treatment at haemophilia treatment centres requires a multidisciplinary approach involving at least a haematologist, a nurse, a physical therapist, and a psychosocial professional (Zhou). In this study. there were 13 (PLwH=10, HCP=3) references to fear, such as “Fear of getting injured in social outings” (HCP), “I have sleepless nights due to fear of bleeding” (Patient), and ‘...The fear of bleeding as a result of being wounded” (patient). It is therefore important to engage more psychosocial experts in the management of haemophilia in southern Nigeria. The use of trained patient navigators supported by virtual counsellors can help to address the gap in psychosocial care, as demonstrated by a Nigerian study involving cancer patients.¹⁷ Contrary to what was previously assumed during the project design, this study did not find any statistically significant difference in perceptions of stigma between HCPs and PLwH, as fewer than 45% of participants in both groups perceived stigma to be a barrier. One patient and one HCP, however, summarized the perceptions of stigma:

“Personally, as a patient, there is social isolation that you feel because of your inability to do other

things you were supposed to do as a normal person" (patient).

"There is frustration and isolation to avoid injuries and bleeding" (HCP)

CONCLUSION

Although hemophilia is a rare disease it affects a significant number of people in Nigeria to warrant increasing attention. This mixed methods study sought to explore the barriers and knowledge gaps (i.e. needs assessment) related to haemophilia in southern Nigeria. Using a high level of scientific rigour, the study found that knowledge about haemophilia was low among patients and healthcare professionals. This exemplified the educational barriers that affected the care patients received. One approach to address the educational barriers is to invest in the continuing education of HCPs. Technical barriers identified included inadequacy of the number of clinicians, challenges with laboratory diagnosis, and logistics to access treatment products and their storage. Expanding the number of haemophilia treatment centres in Nigeria would help address many of the technical barriers.

Furthermore, Nigerian hemophilia patients faced financial barriers due to worsening economic conditions which affected their abilities to pay for services relevant to their treatment as well as difficulties with employment. The study identified anxiety and depression, lack of counselling/psychosocial support and stigma as the major psychosocial barriers that patients face. Also, PLwH in Nigeria face significant psychosocial challenges which are not adequately met by their HCPs. About 71% of HCPs and 49% of PLwH identified significant mental health challenges for patients but also highlighted the absence of counselling services to meet these needs. The use of patient navigators and remote counselling services have been proposed as measures to address these barriers. The government can help to improve the quality of lives of PLwH by addressing these barriers

through providing financial support and improving access to psychological counseling. Further studies are needed to evaluate the impact of future educational and psychosocial interventions on the quality of life of hemophilia patients.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in this study

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All the authors participated in the design, conduct and writing of this study. All authors also consented to the publication of this study

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